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Prevalence of intestinal parasitosis in farmed white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) in farms in the Gulf of Venezuela.

Prevalencia de parasitosis intestinal en camarón blanco (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) de cultivo en granjas del Golfo de Venezuela

Edison Pascal^{1,2*}, Helimar Vásquez²

¹ Center for Molecular Biomedicine, Venezuelan Institute of Scientific Research (IVIC). Maracaibo, Venezuela. Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5108-1889>

² Parasitological Research Unit, Faculty of Veterinary Sciences, University of Zulia (LUZ). Maracaibo, Venezuela. Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2505-7850>

* Corresponding author: Edison Pascal <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5108-1889>

E-mail: edisonpascal@gmail.com / edison.pascal@fcv.edu.luz.ve

Abstract

Litopenaeus vannamei is a decapod crustacean widely used in aquaculture. One of the fundamental aspects in its cultivation is aquaculture health, since the lack of periodic clinical evaluations and the lack of trained personnel can lead to the spread of diseases between ponds or lagoons. One of the factors that affects the health of these animals is parasitosis, specifically intestinal parasitosis. This research aims to analyze the prevalence of intestinal parasitosis in farmed white shrimp (*L. vannamei*) on farms in the Gulf of Venezuela. The research was carried out on the western coast of the Falcón state, specifically in the coastal area of the Mauroa municipality, in the Gulf of Venezuela. In this area there are several shrimp farms, including the farms used for the research (three farms), which were classified as A, B, and C. The shrimp were sampled with a fishing net (cast net) by making random casts into the ponds, the animals were transferred to the laboratory for pathological analysis. It was detected that the intestinal infection was caused by the apicomplexan protozoan *Nematopsis* sp; the prevalence was composed of A: 28.1625; B: 30.1375 and C: 27.362222. In the statistical analysis (with the Kruskal-Wallis test) an H value was obtained: 3.9720930232558174, and a p value: 0.13723691890929887, demonstrating that there is no statistically significant difference in the prevalence of the disease between the three groups. studied in this essay.

Resumen

Litopenaeus vannamei es un crustáceo decápodo ampliamente empleado en la acuicultura. Uno de los aspectos fundamentales en su cultivo es la salud acuícola, ya que la falta de evaluaciones clínicas periódicas y la carencia de personal capacitado pueden propiciar la propagación de enfermedades entre estanques o lagunas. Uno de los factores que afecta la salud de estos animales son las parasitosis, específicamente, las parasitosis intestinales. Esta investigación tiene como objetivo, analizar la Prevalencia de parasitosis intestinales en camarón blanco de cultivo (*L. vannamei*) en fincas del Golfo de Venezuela. La investigación se llevó a cabo en la costa occidental del estado Falcón, específicamente en la zona costera del municipio Mauroa, en el Golfo de Venezuela. En esta zona se encuentran varias fincas camaronerías, incluyendo las fincas utilizadas para la investigación (tres fincas), las cuales se clasificaron como A, B y C. Los camarones fueron muestreados con red de pesca (atarraya) realizando lanzamientos aleatorios dentro de los estanques, los animales fueron trasladados al laboratorio para realizar análisis patológico. Se detectó que la infección intestinal fue causada por el protozooario apicomplejo *Nematopsis* sp; la prevalencia estuvo compuesta por A: 28,1625; B: 30,1375 y C: 27,36222222. En el análisis estadístico (con la prueba de Kruskal-Wallis) se obtuvo un valor de H: 3.9720930232558174, y un valor de p: 0.13723691890929887, demostrando esto que, no existe una diferencia estadísticamente significativa en la prevalencia de la enfermedad entre los tres grupos estudiados en este ensayo.

Palabras clave: Parasitosis, camarón, prevalencia

Keywords: Parasitosis, shrimp, prevalence

Introduction

The white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) is a decapod crustacean widely used in aquaculture. One of the fundamental aspects in its cultivation is aquaculture health, since the lack of periodic clinical evaluations and the lack of trained personnel can lead to the spread of diseases between ponds or lagoons (4).

Farms present in the same region or geographic area may present problems with the spread of diseases in shrimp populations. The partial or total loss of a shrimp population due to disease can go unnoticed if proper evaluations and diagnoses of the health status of these crustaceans are not carried out. Therefore, it is essential to carry out periodic clinical evaluations and have trained personnel to prevent the spread of diseases between culture ponds (6).

In farmed shrimp, various diseases and causal agents have been identified, among which are parasitic diseases. These parasites are organisms that develop at the expense of others of a different species, obtaining their food or substances produced by the host, which can be harmful in some cases, even causing the death of the host. Shrimp cultures have been affected by outbreaks of various pathogenic agents, mainly viruses and bacteria, and to a lesser extent fungi and parasites, affecting them in various ways (4,13).

A parasite is an organism that lives at the expense of another organism of a different species, feeding directly on the substances that it consumes or produces. This interaction may or may not be harmful, in some cases it could cause the death of the host. In the case of shrimp, there are endoparasites and ectoparasites capable of producing mild or severe infestations, which are called "Parasitosis" (1).

Shrimp diseases in recent times have characteristics associated with many physicochemical factors, as well as intestinal protozoan parasites present in ponds or culture pools. For this reason, it is necessary to identify the causes of such pathologies, and to determine the influence of environmental patterns on shrimp (3).

Among the parasitic protozoans that cause intestinal diseases in shrimp, we have the gregarines, which are Apicomplexans of many types. The most common genera in farmed shrimp are *Nematopsis* and *Cephalolobus*. There is a third genus rarely observed in *L. vannamei* postlarvae called *Paraophioidina* (1).

In a study carried out in 2002, where the presence of gregarines was evaluated in several shrimp farms, an animal infection of 50 to 80 percent was obtained, with a parasite load of 10 to 5,000 gregarines per animal, it was determined that The postlarvae before sowing did not contain this parasitic protozoan, demonstrating that the infection occurred in the farms' ponds or pools. This parasitosis is associated with the marine or aquatic environment, without the parasite having been detected in freshwater or low salinity shrimp (10,11).

From this perspective, significant efforts have been carried out to determine the prevalence of diseases in different producing areas of the American continent and the world, including in wild species that can serve as vectors of parasitic and other diseases. These studies make it possible to identify and control these pathologies in shrimp, improving the production and well-being of these crustacean populations. The prevalence of parasitic diseases in different producing areas of the planet is a fundamental animal health issue, since these diseases can seriously affect food production and the economy of the affected regions. Parasitic diseases, in particular, are caused by organisms that live at the expense of other living beings and can affect shrimp, causing diseases and damage to their culture (4).

Based on these premises, this research aims to analyze the prevalence of intestinal parasitosis in farmed white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) in farms in the Gulf of Venezuela.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The research was carried out on the western coast of the Falcón state, specifically in the coastal area of the Mauroa municipality, in the Gulf of Venezuela. In this area there are several shrimp farms, including the farms used for research (three farms), which we will classify as A, B and C. Farms A and B are located adjacent to the town of Casigua at coordinates 11°02'59" N 71°04'12" W.

Farm C is located bordering the border with the western state of Zulia, surrounding the border between the municipalities of Miranda (Zulia) and Mauroa (Falcón). This farm is located near the town of San Félix (Mauroa-Falcón), whose coordinates are: 10°55'23"N 71°11'13"W.

The animals were collected in these previously described farms, in a cultivation period, comprising the interval of 5 months corresponding from May to October 2022.

Animal Sampling and Diagnosis of Intestinal Parasitosis

The shrimp were collected using a cast net (round fishing net with weights in the circumference and a rope fixed to the center of the net that is thrown from the shore of the farming lagoons to capture the animals) of 2 meters in diameter, making throws randomly at different points in the ponds or lagoons. Subsequently, the animals are collected in plastic containers and are immediately transferred to the laboratory for analysis of intestinal contents. During this examination, specific attention was paid to the particular symptoms of possible intestinal parasitosis. The diagnostic method used to detect intestinal parasites was fresh mounting, which was performed by optical microscopy using 10x and 40x objectives. It should be noted that no type of staining was required for the identification of intestinal parasites (5,9).

Calculation of Prevalence of Intestinal Parasitosis

The prevalence calculation refers to the proportion of cases of the disease (parasitosis) in the shrimp population in a specific period. To determine the frequency of the parasitic disease, the formula described by Peña and Varela was applied (7).

$$N/Nt \times 100=P$$

Where:

P: Prevalence

N: No. of hosts with parasites

Nt: Total number of hosts

Statistical Analysis of the Prevalence of Intestinal Parasitic Diseases in the Three Shrimp Farms

Tables of average {x} of the Prevalence will be made and the Kruskal-Wallis statistical analysis will be used, using the following formula:

$$H= 12/N(N+1) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^g Ri^2/ ni - 3(N+1)$$

Where:

N: is the total number of observations in all groups

g: is the number of groups

Ri: is the sum of ranks of the group

ni: is the number of observations in the group.

This test is used to compare the prevalence of a disease in more than two categorical groups. It is based on the comparison of the means of the observations in the different groups, and it is assumed that the data do not have a normal distribution (8).

Results and discussion

Study of Clinical and Laboratory Characteristics for the Detection of Intestinal Parasites of *L. vannamei*

To take samples in the field, the clinical characteristics of the animals were examined in order to detect the presence of intestinal parasites (mainly protozoa), for example, the yellow appearance in the intestine area. It is important to note that, during field sampling, no characteristic related to the infection caused by these parasites was observed.

However, in the laboratory analysis, infection could be noted at the intestinal level (through fresh analysis). For the aforementioned study, the intestinal contents of *L. vannamei* were extracted and the presence or absence of intestinal parasites was identified. In the case of this research, the apicomplexan protozoan *Nematopsis* sp (Gregarinas – Figure 1) was identified in the intestinal contents of crustaceans, considering the number of infected animals in each sample(6). Gregarine trophozoites of the genus *Nematopsis* sp are commonly found in the midgut of *L. vannamei*, although they have also been found sporadically in the stomach and hepatopancreas. On the other hand, Apicomplexans of the genus *Nematopsis* sp are usually located in the midgut or rectum, unlike other genera of gregarines, such as *Cephalolobus* sp, which is generally found in the mouthparts of *L. vannamei* or in its stomach (2).

Figure 1. Trophozoite (left side of the image) of *Nematopsis* sp, an apicomplexan protozoan found in the intestinal contents of *L. vannamei*. You can also notice some syzygies on the right side of the image (Source: Pascal y Vásquez).

Period	Farm A	Farm B	Farm C
May-jun	25	23	20
July	28	29	22,61
August	27,65	30,55	25,00
September	35,5	35,83	27,87
October	32	38	30,23
Average	28,1625	30,1375	27,3622

Table 1. Average (for each period, and total) of the prevalence of intestinal parasitosis in the three farms studied for this trial (Source: Pascal and Vásquez).

Likewise, the presence of syzygia could be noted (Figure 1. Far right), which correspond to a juvenile stage of the trophozoite of *Nematopsis* sp. It can be seen that the syzygy is lighter in color, compared to the trophozoite, dark brown.

The gregarines of the genus *Nematopsis* are the ones that occur most frequently (as intestinal parasites) in *L. vannamei*, managing to infect the ponds due to the presence of some polychaetes and/or bivalve mollusks (which serve as intermediate hosts), or by direct ingestion of fecal material (3).

In table 1, we can see the prevalence of parasitosis caused by gregarines during this trial, where it is highlighted that the highest average prevalence was obtained by farm B.

Figure 2. Bar graph relating the prevalence obtained for each farm. Farm A in blue, Farm B in red and Farm C in gray (Source: Pascal y Vásquez).

However, in Figure 2, it can be noted that the prevalence in the three farms did not present significant differences; however, the highest prevalence (in this trial) was observed for farm B, in the month of October (38%).

In other studies carried out on prevalence in Shrimp, a maximum prevalence of 20% has been observed in gregarines for shrimp farms throughout Latin America (12). This contrasts with what was obtained in this research, whose average prevalence (Table 1) exceeded (slightly) that established by the previously mentioned researchers. However, no damage was observed at the intestinal level in the shrimp, the characteristic signs being of this parasitosis, empty intestine or hyperplasia, which affects the absorption capacity of this organ.

Statistical Evaluation of the Prevalence of Intestinal Parasitic Diseases

Figure 3. Histogram illustrating the density distributions of the prevalence rates of the three groups labeled A, B and C (Source: Pascal and Vásquez).

Figure 3 shows the density distribution of the prevalence rates of the three groups. Prevalence refers to the proportion of individuals in a population who have a specific disease or condition at a given time. The histogram shows how the prevalence rates are distributed across the three groups and how they overlap with each other. The overlap in this histogram indicates similarities in the prevalence of parasitosis between the groups of animals (from each farm) analyzed in this experiment.

Kruskal-Wallis Test

The objective of the Kruskal-Wallis test was to determine if there were significant differences between the means of samples A, B and C. For this, the H statistic was used and it was compared with a distribution cut-off point.

Kruskal-Wallis H: 3.9720930232558174

P: 0.13723691890929887

The Kruskal-Wallis test was performed, yielding a test statistic of approximately 3.97 and a p-value of approximately 0.137. Since the p-value is greater than the common alpha level of 0.05, we do not reject the null hypothesis; This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the prevalence of the disease between the three groups; That is, the test indicates that there is no significant discrepancy in the prevalence of the parasitic disease (caused by the apicomplexan protozoan *Nematopsis* sp) between the

groups of farms A, B and C, since the p value exceeds the level typical alpha of 0.05. Likewise, this trend could be observed in the bar graph (Figure 2) and in the histogram (Figure 3), before performing the Kruskal-Wallis statistical analysis.

Conclusion

Parasitosis caused by gregarines (of the genus *Nematopsis* sp) constitutes the only intestinal parasitosis found in the area of the shrimp farms studied.

Although the prevalence (in all the farms used for this trial) exceeded 20%, no damage was determined at the level of the intestinal epithelium in the marine animals affected by the parasitosis.

The statistical test (Kruskal-Wallis test) revealed no statistically significant difference in the prevalence of the disease between the groups affected by parasitosis and studied in this trial.

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